

Improper waste managements: Effects on physical, chemical and heavy metals of municipal dumpsite soils in Ogbomoso, Nigeria

Folasade Mary Owoade^{*1}, Oluwatobiloba Esther Adegbite¹; Abdulbashit Oladipupo¹,
Blessing Jennifer Onyemachi¹, Jumoke Deborah Olowolagba¹,
Adetola Mohammed Adedokun¹, Benjunior Ugochukwu Alor¹, Peter Wusu Olugbemi²

¹Department of Crop Production and Soil Science, Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, P.M.B. 4000, Ogbomoso, Oyo State, Nigeria,

²Department of Agricultural Education, College of Vocational and Entrepreneurship Education, Lagos State University of Education, Lagos, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: fmowoade@lautech.edu.ng; Telephone: +2348034229124

Abstract

Most farmers in developing country like Nigeria have resulted to the use of solid wastes as compost to replenish the deteriorated soils while some are farming on the abandoned waste dumpsite due to the richness of such sites in organic matter. This study assessed the soil nutrient and fertility status by investigating the influence of wastes on physical and chemical properties of soils in and around selected dumpsites in Ogbomoso, Nigeria for environmental sustainability. In order to evaluate the effects of municipal solid waste dumpsites on soils, top, middle and down sites soils were collected with the aid of a graduated soil auger at a depth of 15 cm. Samples were also taken 50 m away from dumpsites which served as control. Samples taken were analysed in the laboratory to determine the level of physical and chemical properties such as: pH, particle size distribution, bulk density, Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity (SHC), Organic Carbon (OC), Field Capacity, Wilting Point, Plant Available Water and heavy metals (Zn, Fe, Pb) using standard methods. The findings showed that the bulk density (0.42 – 1.70 g/cm³) and pH 7.1 (slightly alkaline) - 8.8 (alkaline); organic carbon (1.3 - 3.1%) and SHC (1.35-5.61 cm/hr) were higher in the polluted area than the control. The results further indicated that the heavy metals with values above the control and permissible limits posed the greatest danger to animals and humans. Therefore, there is need for proper management of municipal solid wastes in Ogbomoso town.

Keywords: Municipal dumpsite; Environmental sustainability; Soil properties; Heavy metals

Introduction

Most serious problem in Ogbomoso and in most cities in Nigeria is improper wastes disposal. Solid waste is garbage, refuse or trash which is on the rise mostly in developing countries without adequate management (Salam, 2010). In Nigeria, leachates from refuse dumpsites constitutes a source of heavy pollution to both soil and aquatic environment. In Ogbomoso, waste are dumped recklessly with no regards to the environmental implications, while in some dumpsites, waste is burnt in the open and ashes abandoned at the sites.

Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) which is commonly known as trash or garbage consists of everyday items we use and then throw away such as product packaging, grass clippings, furniture, clothing, bottles, food scraps, newspapers, appliances and so on. These items come from households, schools, offices, market places, restaurants and other public places (U.S. EPA, 2016). Municipal solid waste has become a major environmental challenge. The

manner and way in which solid wastes are being disposed is a major concern from lack of waste reduction, to illegal dumping of wastes indiscriminately to its poor management in Nigeria. In most cases the wastes are indiscriminately disposed of, the net impact results in obstruction of drainages and causes pollution to water bodies due to lack of effective and efficient waste management program in many towns and cities (Adeniran *et al.*, 2017).

The landfill strategy is still in practice worldwide and very common, it has been the principal method of municipal waste elimination in the recent decades because it is the simplest practice and the most economical type of waste management in many developing countries. (Breza-Boruta *et al.*, 2016). Unfortunately, these open landfills cause serious sanitary risks by the lodging of different stray animals and the proliferation of insect vectors of a lot of diseases. They also present nuisance and considerable environmental impacts by the

production of both leachate and biogas (Aronsson *et al.*, 2010).

In Nigeria, leachates from refuse dumpsites constitutes a source of heavy metal pollution to both soil and aquatic environment (Obaliagbon & Olowojoba 2007). In some areas, waste are dumped recklessly with no regards to the environmental implications, while in some dumpsites, waste is burnt in the open and ashes abandoned at the sites. The burning of waste get rids of the organic materials and oxidized the metals leaving the ash richer in metal contents. After the process of oxidation and corrosion, these metals will dissolve in rain water and leached into the soil from where they are picked up by growing plants, thereby entering the food chain. Moreover, according to Njoiju & Ayoka, 2006, improper waste management methods also leads to contamination of underground water, while most of the metals are being washed away by runoff into streams and rivers thus contaminating the marine environment. Consequently, these metals accumulate in fish and other organisms (aquatic) hence posing a health threat to the consumers.

The great concern in the last decades is land pollution as a result of the component of refuse such as heavy metals which result into health hazards to man and other organisms when accumulated with a biological system (Adekunle *et al.*, 2003). Many researchers have shown that waste dumpsite can transfer significant levels of these toxic and persistent metals into the soil environment. Eventually, these metals are taken up by plant part and transfer same into the food chain. Consequently, higher soil heavy metals concentration can result in higher levels of uptake by plants (Amadi & Nwankwoala, 2013). Uzoho & Oti (2006), reported that in some places, most of the dumpsites are used as fertile soils for the cultivation of some fruits and vegetables. Some farmers collect the decomposed parts of the dumpsites and apply to their farms as manure. These cultivated plants take up these heavy metals either as mobile ion in the soil solution through their roots or leaves thereby making it unfit for human consumption. Heavy metals are metals with a density of at least five times that of water (Hawkes 1997,). It is the term commonly adopted as a group name for the metals which are associated with pollution and toxicity.

Heavy metals may also include some elements which are very essential for living organisms at low concentrations. Among these heavy metals some (As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Hg, Ni, Al and Zn) have been found to be of serious hazards to plants and animals. In the last 50 years, human intoxication by heavy metals had risen drastically due to an exponential increase in the use of heavy metals in industrial processes and other human activities like refuse dumping, agricultural activities and industrial activities. Heavy metal toxicity means excess of required concentration or it is unwanted which were found naturally on the earth, and become concentrated as a result of human caused activities, enter in plant, animal and human tissues via inhalation, diet and manual handling, and can bind to, and interfere with the functioning of vital cellular components (Asati *et al.*, 2016).

Research conducted on physical and chemical properties and heavy metal contents from the soil within some solid waste dumpsites in other countries and Nigeria shows that solid wastes affects the soil properties within the solid waste dumpsites (Amadi & Nwankwoala, 2013). Eneja and Lemoha (2012) also reported that the properties and heavy metals concentration of soil within the solid waste dumpsites varies and this depends on the composition and characterization of the solid wastes and the peculiarities of the neighborhood activities.

Materials and methods

Experimental site

The study was carried out in Ogbomoso Agricultural Zone, Oyo State, south-western Nigeria. The study area lies between latitude 8.1421° N, of the equator and longitude 4.2436°E of the Greenwich Meridian. Ogbomoso experiences two local climates (rainy and dry seasons). The rainy season is from March to October and the dry season from November to February, with an average annual rainfall of 1070 mm (42.1 inch). The average annual temperature in Ogbomoso is 26.1°C. With an estimated population of 354,690 (2006 census) 551,474 (est. 2020), the average waste generation per capita per day is about 0.13 kg/capita/day in Ogbomoso. However, not all the wastes were disposed off at the dumpsites (Nnaji, 2015).

Soil sampling and preparation

Eight dumpsites were chosen for this study from eight different locations within Ogbomoso town. The areas under studied were Jagun, Sawmill, Stadium, LAUTECH, Abogunde, Isoko, Laka and Ibaon. The samples were collected between August 17th and August 20th, 2021.

Soil samples were collected at 15 cm depth with a hand-held sampling soil auger. At each dumpsite, three (3) points were chosen for sample collection and were labelled as Top site which represented freshly dumped wastes, Middle site which represented the partially decomposed waste and the Down site which represented the fully decomposed waste. On each of these sites, three samples were taken in a triangular form at the Top site (T), Middle site (M) and Down site (D). The control soil samples were obtained in the same way (50 m away from each dumpsite). The control site was an unaffected waste-free sites.

Each soil sample was then placed in a polythene bag, air dried, crushed and were made to pass through 2-mm stainless steel sieve.

Laboratory analyses

The physical and chemical properties of the soil samples were determined using standard analytical methods. The chemical analysis includes; soil pH which was determined by immersing a glass electrode (H1 9017) microprocessor pH meter in a ratio of 1:2 soil-water suspension; Heavy metals concentrations; Iron (Fe), Zinc (Zn) and Lead (Pb) in the soil samples were analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) (Spectra 200). Soil organic carbon content was also determined using the Walkley-Black Method. The physical analysis conducted was the Grain Size distribution test using the hydrometer method by means of sodium hexametaphosphate as dispersant. Other analyses including Bulk density, Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity, Saturation, Field capacity, wilting point and Plant available water were carried out using Pedosphere.ca 2012 Software Package.

Statistical analysis

The experimental data from each treatment were subjected to Analysis of variance and significant means were compared using Least Significant Differences (LSD), at the confidence level of $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion

Physical properties

The results of the particle size analysis and bulk density of the soils from the eight sampled locations in each dump sites are presented in Table 1. The particle size distribution characteristics of the soil showed that sand had the highest percentage value ranging from 65.15 to 94.20%, silt had values between 2.75 and 21.86% while clay had the lowest value which ranged from 2.43 to 12.99%. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the values of clay, silt and sand between the samples collected on the dumpsites and samples collected at the control site at $P = 0.05$ and this indicated that the wastes may affect the structure of the soil in terms of firmness due to the presence of organic matter from the deposition of wastes. Percentage of sand, silt and clay in soils from the top site, middle site and down site indicated that they had loamy sand and sandy loam texture while the control sites were mainly sand. Indorrial *et al.* (2017) stated that the nature and quality of soil structure are strongly affected by the quantity and quality of organic matter in the soil. Thus, soils from the dumpsite will have more stable structure, high moisture content, water retention and porosity, low soil strength and bulk density and this in turn strengthen the root growth of the plants by moving the nutrients into the surface and subsurface soils (Gurber *et al.*, 2014; Hatten and Lilles, 2019).

Additionally, an increase in sand fraction in the dumpsite causes leaching of high pollutant, because the clay contents and organic matter in colloids are accountable for retaining metallic ions in soils (Ruth *et al.*, 2021). This is because soils with 75% sand content have not too strong soil accumulation at the surface and thus liable to porosity, air circulation, leaching and easily transportable (Gbadegesin and Abua, 2011; Eyankware *et al.*, 2016).

Table 1: Particle analysis and bulk density of the soil samples from the dumpsites in Ogbomoso, Nigeria

LGA	Town Location	Sample Location	GPS Location	% Sand	% Silt	% Clay	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Textural Class
Ogbomoso North	JAGUN	Control	8° 2' 17" N, 4° 19' 30" E	88.36	6.73	4.91	0.27	Sand
		Top site		77.70	14.29	8.01	1.18	Sandy loam
		Middle site		73.82	18.38	7.80	1.46	Sandy loam
		Down site		65.15	21.86	12.99	1.45	Sandy loam
	LAUTECH	Control	8° 8' 0" N, 4° 16' 0" E	85.70	9.54	4.76	0.27	Sand
		Top site		78.70	13.62	7.68	1.19	Loamy sand
		Middle site		87.49	4.71	7.80	1.49	Loamy sand
		Down site		85.82	7.99	6.19	1.59	Loamy sand
	SAWMILL	Control	8.123975 N, 4.218886 E	89.70	6.06	4.24	0.27	Sand
		Top site		83.36	8.96	7.68	1.20	Loamy sand
		Middle site		80.82	11.38	7.80	1.48	Loamy sand
		Down site		77.15	14.53	8.32	1.52	Sandy loam
STADIUM	Control	8° 8' 31.79" N, 4° 14' 42.66" E	92.34	2.75	4.91	0.82	Sand	
	Top site		82.70	9.62	7.68	1.20	Loamy sand	
	Middle site		81.49	10.71	7.80	1.48	Loamy sand	
	Down site		89.15	3.19	7.66	1.57	Sand	
ABOGUNDE	Control	8.11791° N, 4.23709° E	87.53	5.94	6.53	0.24	Loamy sand	
	Top site		81.86	9.04	9.10	1.45	Loamy sand	
	Middle site		79.07	12.63	8.30	1.75	Loamy sand	
	Down site		82.40	7.82	9.78	1.09	Loamy sand	
IBAPON	Control	8.1067° N, 4.1850° E	94.20	3.93	1.87	0.27	Sand	
	Top site		89.20	8.37	2.43	0.42	Sand	
	Middle site		87.07	6.63	6.30	0.66	Loamy sand	
	Down site		78.40	14.48	7.12	1.70	Loamy sand	
ISOKO	Control	8.0821° N, 4.2357° E	87.53	6.58	5.87	1.38	Loamy sand	
	Top site		75.53	17.37	7.10	0.94	Sandy loam	
	Middle site		78.40	15.30	6.30	1.78	Loamy sand	
	Down site		78.07	12.81	9.12	1.67	Sandy loam	
LAKA	Control	8.0732° N, 4.23658° E	86.86	8.61	4.53	0.28	Loamy sand	
	Top site		75.86	11.71	12.43	1.97	Sandy loam	
	Middle site		79.07	10.63	10.30	1.72	Sandy loam	
	Down site		78.40	12.48	9.12	1.67	Sandy loam	
LGA LSD (0.05)				1.47	1.21	1.08	0.18	
Sample Location LSD (0.05)				2.07*	1.72*	1.53*	0.26*	
Town Location LSD (0.05)				2.93	2.43	2.16	0.36	
Sample and Town Location LSD (0.05)				5.87	4.85	4.31	0.73	

LSD (0.05) = Least Significant Difference at 5% level of probability; LGA = Local Government Area

The highest values of bulk density ($1.09-1.70 \text{ g/cm}^3$) of the soils were recorded from the down site of the dumpsite followed by the middle site soils ($0.66-1.78 \text{ g/cm}^3$), followed by the top site soils ($0.42-1.97 \text{ g/cm}^3$) while the control site soils had the lowest bulk density value of 0.24 g/cm^3 ; only the control sites had a very low bulk density whereas other sites in all the locations have a high bulk density. This is ideal for growth based on the textural class according to Arshad *et al.* (1996). It was observed that the bulk density of the soil decreases with increase in the % of sand content and porosity of the soils. Significant differences were also noticed in the values of the bulk density from soils at the dumpsites and soils obtained from the control sites at $P=0.05$.

Significant differences observed among the sampling locations with respect to bulk density and porosity could be ascribed to the differences in soil organic matter content that enhances pore spaces and put soil aggregates together (Brevik, 2014). The significantly lower bulk density and high porosity values recorded from the control soils when compared to the soils at the dumpsites of each location is in line with similar work conducted by Njoku (2015) and Agbeshie *et al.* (2020). Thus, soils from dumpsite will be more beneficial to root penetration for firmness and support (Doran and Zeiss, 2000) and the determined physical conditions from dumpsite soils are greatly affected when compared to soils from the control sites due to the quality and quantity of organic matter present (Karak *et al.*, 2012; Indorinal *et al.*, 2017) as a result of wastes decomposition.

The result of ANOVA for Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity (SHC) (cm/hr), Saturation ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ water/cm}^3 \text{ soil}$), Wilting point ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ water/cm}^3 \text{ soil}$), Plant available Water (PAW) ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ water/cm}^3 \text{ soil}$) and Field Capacity ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ water/cm}^3 \text{ soil}$) are presented in Table 2.

Chemical Properties

The pH values of the studied samples presents in Table 3 ranged from 7.1 to 8.8 which indicated that all the dumpsites were moderately alkaline. This is higher than the values (4.8- 7.66) obtained by Obianefo *et al.* (2017) but within the earlier findings on dumpsites by Obasi *et al.* (2012); Osunwoke and Kurofiji (2012); Saida *et al.* (2019) and Enerijiofi and Ekhaise (2019) and Agbeshie *et al.* (2020). The significantly higher pH values recorded in the dumpsite soils could be attributed to the presence of high quantity of liming material, and biological activities (soil microorganism) on the solid wastes (Osei *et al.*, 2011; Kebede *et al.*, 2016; Agbeshie *et al.*, 2020). Generally, it has been reported that pH has unswerving relationship with soil chemical properties and nutrients is made available to plants in high concentration at pH value of 6.5-7.5 (Akintola *et al.*, 2021; Praveena and Rao, 2016). Thus, it is a major property that determines numerous chemical processes that occur in soil (Ahmed *et al.*, 2014).

Soil samples from the studied locations had organic carbon content ranging from 0.8 to 3.4%. Highest mean values of organic carbon were observed from soils collected from the dumpsites except for the control which showed a low level of organic carbon. Significant differences were also observed between the soils at each dumpsite and soils from the control sites at $P=0.05$. Significantly higher mean values of organic carbon content observed from dumpsite soils when compared to control site soils could be due to the decomposition of organic wastes by soil microbial activities that has led to increase in the soil organic matter contents which serve as major source of nitrogen and phosphorus for plant growth (Obute *et al.*, 2010, Amos-Tautua *et al.*, 2014). High values of organic carbon recorded from dumpsite soils when compared with the control sites were in line with the results of previous researchers (Obianefo *et al.*, 2017; Agbeshie *et al.*, 2020).

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Table 2: Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity, Saturation, Field Capacity, Wilting Point and Plant Available Water of the soil samples from dumpsites in Ogbomoso, Nigeria

LGA	Town Location	Sample Location	SHC (cm/hr)	Saturation (cm ³ water/ cm ³ soil)	Wilting point (cm ³ water/ cm ³ soil)	PAW (cm ³ water/ cm ³ soil)	Field Capacity (cm ³ water/ cm ³ soil)	
Ogbomoso North	JAGUN	Control	0.72	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.03	
		Top site	2.32	0.30	0.06	0.07	0.13	
		Middle site	3.43	0.36	0.07	0.09	0.16	
		Down site	Control	1.56	0.41	0.10	0.10	0.20
			Top site	0.72	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.03
			Middle site	2.56	0.30	0.06	0.07	0.13
	LAUTECH	Down site	4.15	0.35	0.07	0.07	0.14	
		Control	5.26	0.36	0.06	0.07	0.14	
		Top site	0.72	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.03	
	SAWMILL	Top site	2.81	0.29	0.06	0.06	0.12	
		Middle site	3.76	0.36	0.08	0.08	0.15	
		Down site	3.03	0.38	0.08	0.08	0.16	
	STADIUM	Control	2.73	0.19	0.04	0.04	0.07	
		Top site	2.75	0.29	0.06	0.06	0.12	
		Middle site	3.82	0.36	0.07	0.08	0.15	
ABOGUNDE	Down site	Control	4.35	0.36	0.07	0.07	0.14	
		Top site	0.10	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.03	
		Middle site	2.92	0.37	0.08	0.08	0.16	
IBAPON	Down site	Control	4.60	0.42	0.08	0.09	0.17	
		Top site	1.35	0.30	0.07	0.06	0.13	
		Middle site	0.72	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.03	
ISOKO	Down site	Control	1.68	0.09	0.01	0.02	0.04	
		Top site	1.37	0.17	0.04	0.04	0.07	
		Middle site	4.96	0.40	0.07	0.09	0.17	
LAKA	Down site	Control	4.65	0.31	0.05	0.06	0.12	
		Top site	2.30	0.23	0.04	0.05	0.10	
		Middle site	5.61	0.41	0.07	0.10	0.17	
LGA LSD (0.05)	Down site	Control	3.93	0.41	0.08	0.09	0.17	
		Top site	1.05	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.02	
		Middle site	3.54	0.50	0.11	0.11	0.22	
Sample Location LSD (0.05)	Down site	Control	3.59	0.43	0.09	0.09	0.18	
		Top site	3.96	0.41	0.08	0.09	0.17	
		Middle site	0.506	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.02	
Town Location LSD (0.05)	Down site	Control	0.715	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.03	
		Top site	1.012	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.04	
		Middle site	2.023	0.19	0.04	0.04	0.08	
Sample and Town Location LSD (0.05)								

LSD (0.05) = Least Significant Difference at 5% level of proba

Table 3: Chemical properties of the soil samples from dumpsites in Ogbomoso, Nigeria

LGA	Town Location	Sample Location	%Organic Carbon	pH (H ₂ O) 1:2	
Ogbomoso North	JAGUN	Control	2.6	7.3	
		Top site	2.4	8.2	
		Middle site	2.3	7.5	
		Down site	2.3	8.1	
	LAUTECH	Control	1.2	8.2	
		Top site	2.6	8.2	
		Middle site	2.8	8.4	
		Down site	2.4	7.9	
	SAWMILL	Control	1.1	7.6	
		Top site	2.9	8.2	
		Middle site	2.1	7.5	
		Down site	3.3	7.6	
	STADIUM	Control	0.8	7.5	
		Top site	2.7	8.0	
		Middle site	3.1	8.1	
		Down site	1.5	7.7	
	Ogbomoso South	ABOGUNDE	Control	1.3	8.1
			Top site	3.1	8.7
			Middle site	3.2	8.3
			Down site	2.4	7.1
IBAPON		Control	1.7	7.2	
		Top site	3.1	8.8	
		Middle site	3.4	8.2	
		Down site	2.7	8.6	
ISOKO		Control	1.2	7.4	
		Top site	2.6	7.7	
		Middle site	2.5	7.9	
		Down site	2.6	7.6	
LAKA		Control	1.6	7.9	
		Top site	1.8	7.8	
		Middle site	1.3	7.7	
		Down site	1.8	7.8	
		LGA LSD (0.05)		0.10	0.08
		Sample Location LSD (0.05)		0.14*	0.11
		Town Location LSD (0.05)		0.20	0.15
		Sample and Town Location LSD (0.05)		0.40	0.30

LSD (0.05) = Least Significant Difference at 5% level of probability

According to Amos-Tautua *et al.* (2014), the high organic carbon content from waste dumpsite soils will have significant influence on soil bulk density, moisture content, porosity, availability of nutrients and plant growth. The carbon that is fixed by plant is transferred to the soil via dead plant matter including dead roots, leaves and fruiting bodies. Organic carbon contents play a crucial role in sustaining soil fertility, crop production and environmental quality due to their effect on soil physical, chemical and biological properties, such as soil water retention, nutrient cycling, gas flux and plant root growth (Prameela and Venugopal Nair, 2020).

Heavy metals concentrations

Table 4 reveals the concentration of Iron (Fe), Zinc (Zn) and Lead (Pb) in the soil samples in the studied areas. Zinc was found to have the highest concentration, ranging from 39.3 to 749.5 mg/kg, followed by Pb which had a concentration ranging from 61.8 to 518.0 mg/kg; while Fe had the least concentration ranging from 76.0 to 506.3 mg/kg. Comparing the town location, sample location and interaction between town location and sample location at 5% level of probability showed no significant effect on the concentration of Zn, Pb and Fe. Heavy metal concentrations in soils are in order of Zn > Pb > Fe. Higher heavy metal concentrations observed in the dumpsite soils agreed with the findings of Njoku (2015) and Agbeshie *et al.* (2020).

Zinc concentration in the studied area were higher than the recommended values given by FAO/WHO (2001), Bowen (1979) and AEP (2016) as presented in Table 5.

Highest Zn concentrations recorded from the dumpsites could be attributable to deposition of materials that are rich in heavy metals such as used battery, electronic materials among others into the dumpsite. As a micronutrient for plant growth, Zn plays an important function in enzyme reaction activities in the soil, thus its relative presence in the soil may lead to reduction in the level of cadmium uptake by plants (Chahab and Savaghebi, 2010).

Lead (Pb) concentration was next to Zinc in the studied areas. Significant differences in Pb concentrations at different locations may be attributed to the deposition of waste materials such as lead pipe, PVC, insecticides, batteries and paints among others on the site (Akintola, 2014). Concentration of Pb in the studied soils were higher than the permissible limit values given by FAO/WHO (2001), Bowen (1979) and AEP (2016) as presented in Table 5.

There were significant differences in Iron (Fe) concentrations at different town locations. Fe concentrations in the studied soils were higher than the recommended values given by some researchers while some Fe concentrations were within the recommended values given by FAO/WHO (2001), Bowen (1979) and AEP (2016) as shown in Table 5. The relatively higher concentrations of Fe in the studied soil may be attributed to its abundance in the earth crust, wastes rich in Fe as well as the mineral composition of the underlying rocks in the studied area. Iron (Fe) is generally needed by plants for nurturing, growth and development (Agbeshie *et al.*, 2020).

Table 4: Concentration of determined heavy metals in the soil samples

LGA	Town Location	Sample Location	Iron (Fe) mg/kg	Lead (Pb) mg/kg	Zinc (Zn) mg/kg
Ogbomoso North	JAGUN	Control	343.4	247.1	719.3
		Top site	393.1	186.2	542.9
		Middle site	447.0	177.8	484.8
		Down site	444.5	295.8	463.6
	LAUTECH	Control	498.6	61.8	276.7
		Top site	255.8	406.6	64.7
		Middle site	314.6	435.6	327.7
		Down site	388.3	156.1	406.3
	SAWMILL	Control	331.5	318.3	727.2
		Top site	243.0	197.1	567.7
		Middle site	309.7	218.1	499.6
		Down site	320.4	283.7	477.0
	STADIUM	Control	325.5	307.5	158.8
		Top site	249.6	334.1	567.8
		Middle site	311.4	211.3	447.3
		Down site	320.9	341.4	397.2

Ogbomoso South	ABOGUNDE	Control	413.3	267.2	516.3
		Top site	190.8	352.2	389.3
		Middle site	106.3	209.0	642.1
		Down site	128.5	518.0	256.5
	IBAPON	Control	76.0	147.7	39.3
		Top site	420.4	178.9	749.5
		Middle site	477.4	175.4	236.0
		Down site	477.6	116.5	277.5
	ISOKO	Control	310.4	349.2	684.8
		Top site	436.8	188.3	274.3
		Middle site	454.1	186.2	621.8
		Down site	409.2	285.7	920.1
	LAKA	Control	354.8	170.6	641.7
		Top site	506.3	404.5	200.6
		Middle site	345.0	472.2	259.4
		Down site	458.8	156.8	290.0
LGA LSD (0.05)			13.20	19.03	34.50
Sample Location LSD (0.05)			18.67	26.92	48.79
Town Location LSD (0.05)			26.41	38.06	69.01
Sample and Location LSD (0.05)			52.82	76.13	13.80

LSD (0.05) = Least Significant Difference at 5% level of probability

Table 5: Permissible limit of Heavy Metals in soil

Heavy Metals (mg/kg)	Fe	Pb	Zn
FAO/ WHO (2001)	100-1000	50	300
Bowen (1979)	100- 700	2-200	100
AEP (2016)	100- 1000	70	200

Source: Akintola *et al.*, (2021)

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicated that municipal solid waste had varying effects on the physical and chemical properties of the studied soils such as bulk density, organic carbon, pH, particle size distribution and heavy metals etc. The study also showed that the dumpsites could also impart some influence on the particle size distribution on soils beneath them. Furthermore, the result gotten from the heavy metals determination showed that the level of contamination of the soil by heavy metals was high, and that the soil was polluted. The heavy metal concentrations in the polluted area were also higher than the permissible background levels based on this study. Elevated concentrations of the heavy metals above WHO standards call for careful monitoring as these persistent metals are capable of accumulation over time along the food chain. This could pose a great danger to animals and humans. It is therefore pertinent to manage municipal solid waste properly in order to minimize their adverse impact on the soil.

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<u>Typic Psammaquant</u>							
Apomu	0-30	A _p	86	7	7	1.00	Sand
	30-60	AB	77	12	11	1.09	sandy loam
	61-100	B1	75	9	15	0.61	sandy loam
	101-160	B2	72	11	17	0.65	sandy loam
	161-210	B3	66	10	24	0.42	sandy clay loam
<u>Aquic Haplustults</u>							
Jago	0-12	A _p	80	6	14	0.43	sandy loam
	13-59	AB	70	10	20	0.50	sandy loam
	60-85	B	68	13	24	0.54	sandy clay loam
<u>Ombroaquic Haplustults</u>							
Origo	0-25	A _p	71	18	11	1.64	sandy loam
	26-62	AB	63	13	24	0.54	sandy clay loam
	63-96	B1	61	12	27	0.44	sandy clay loam
	96-149	B2	52	10	38	0.26	Clay
	150-201	B3	48	16	36	0.44	Clay

Some selected chemical properties of the pedons are shown in Table 3. Soil reaction (pH in water ratio 1:2) ranged from strongly acidic, (pH 4.25 – 5.08) to moderately acidic (pH 5.26 - 5.83) and slightly acidic to neutral reaction (pH 5.90 - 6.73). Iwo series has a moderate acid reaction of (pH 6.06 - 6.17), slightly acidic reaction of (pH 6.3 - 6.49) to a neutral (pH 6.73). Ibadan series has a moderate acid reaction (pH 5.65 -5.96) to slightly acid (pH 6.36). Ondo series exhibited a very strongly acid reaction (pH 4.25 - 4.67) to a strongly acidic reaction (pH 4.93- 4.97). Gambari has a slightly acidic reaction (pH 5.76 - 6.15). Apomu series had a soil pH that was slightly acid (pH 5.05 - 5.64). Jago series pH varies from pH 4.93 to 5.92. Origo series was very strongly acid (pH 4.98 - 5.06). The differences in soil reactions reflect the different leaching environments and the impact of parent materials. The lower horizons of PD 18 (Origo series) show a very strongly acidic (pH 4.13). This could be attributed to the relatively high values of exchangeable Na and or Ca with extractable Al at

this point.

The total Phosphorus distribution was relatively high in all the soil series ranging from 148.13mgkg⁻¹ to 1028.13mgkg⁻¹ (Table 3). Total phosphorus values were relatively high at the epipedon and decreased down the profile. There was an exceptionally high amount of total phosphorus in Iwo series (1028.13 mgkg⁻¹). This could be as a result of continuous application of phosphorus fertilizer and the ability of the soil to retain most of the applied phosphorus. Organic carbon and organic matter content were moderate ranging from 1.30 to 9.54 gkg⁻¹. In all the soils, the organic carbon and organic matter decreased down the profile except in Egbeda, Origo and Apomu series that had higher content in the lower horizons. Percentage total nitrogen was very low in all the soils which decreased down the profile (0.11 to 0.82 %). This could be due to uptake by plant roots, leaching of nitrogen into the subsoil and washing away of the nitrogen content in runoff water. Zinc content was relatively high in

Table 3: Means of Exchangeable Cations, Exchangeable Acidity, ECEC and pH (H₂O)

Soil series	Depth (cm)	Horizon	Ca K Na Mg TEB ECEC TAB CEC							pH (H ₂ O)	
			(Cmol/kg)								
<u>Rhodic Kandiudox</u>											
Egbeda	0-20	A _p	1.07	1.13	1.95	1.79	5.94	7.76	1.82	8.58	5.81
	21-55	AB	0.78	0.82	1.42	1.31	4.34	5.66	1.33	6.26	5.52
	56-97	B1	0.90	0.95	1.63	1.50	4.98	6.50	1.52	7.19	5.67
	98-130	B2	1.25	1.32	2.28	2.09	6.94	9.06	2.12	10.02	5.26
	131-194	B3	0.62	0.72	1.23	1.05	3.62	4.70	1.08	5.19	5.83
<u>Typic Kandiudox</u>											
Itangunmodi	0-25	A _p	0.91	0.95	1.65	1.51	5.02	6.55	1.53	7.25	5.67
	26-50	AB	1.43	1.50	2.59	2.38	7.89	10.31	2.41	11.40	5.75
	51-90	B1	1.68	1.77	3.06	2.80	9.31	12.16	2.85	13.45	5.43
	91-150	B2	1.43	1.51	2.61	2.39	7.93	10.36	2.43	11.46	5.51
	151-200	B3	1.99	2.10	3.62	3.32	11.02	14.40	3.37	15.93	5.51
<u>Arenic Kandiustults</u>											
Iwo	0-25	A _p	1.41	1.49	2.57	2.35	7.82	10.21	2.39	11.30	6.30
	26-59	AB	1.71	1.80	3.11	2.85	9.49	12.39	2.90	13.70	6.73
	60-107	B1	0.80	0.85	1.46	1.34	4.46	5.82	1.36	6.44	6.49
	108-142	B2	0.99	1.05	1.81	1.66	5.51	7.19	1.68	7.96	6.17
	143-198	B3	0.83	0.88	1.52	1.39	4.62	6.04	1.41	6.68	6.06
<u>Kanhaplic Haplustults</u>											
Ibadan	0-20	A _p	0.91	0.96	1.66	1.52	5.06	6.61	1.55	7.31	5.90
	21-56	AB	1.53	1.61	2.78	2.55	8.47	11.05	2.59	12.23	5.96
	57-95	B1	1.92	2.02	3.48	3.19	10.61	13.85	3.24	15.32	5.65
	96-134	B2	2.27	2.39	4.13	3.78	12.56	16.41	3.84	18.15	6.36
	135-190	B3	1.33	1.40	2.42	2.22	7.36	9.61	2.25	10.64	4.36
<u>Udic Paleustalfs</u>											
Gambari	0-15	A _p	0.98	1.03	1.78	1.63	5.41	7.06	1.65	7.81	5.98
	16-75	AB	1.43	1.50	2.60	2.38	7.91	10.33	2.42	11.42	6.15
	76-140	B1	0.54	0.57	0.98	0.90	2.99	3.90	0.91	4.32	5.76
	140-190	B2	0.47	0.49	0.85	0.78	2.58	3.37	0.79	3.73	5.76
<u>PlinthicKandiustults</u>											
Ondo	0-30	A _p	0.77	0.81	1.39	1.28	4.24	5.54	1.30	6.13	4.97
	30-60	AB	0.99	1.04	1.80	1.65	5.48	7.16	1.68	7.92	4.93
	61-100	B1	1.29	1.36	2.35	2.16	7.16	9.36	2.19	10.35	4.66
	101-160	B2	1.24	1.31	2.25	2.07	6.87	8.97	2.10	9.92	4.67
<u>Typic Psammaquant</u>											
Apomu	0-30	A _p	0.59	0.62	1.08	0.99	3.28	4.29	1.00	4.74	5.64
	30-60	AB	0.61	0.65	1.12	1.02	3.40	4.44	1.04	4.91	5.58

	161-210	B3	1.24	1.31	2.26	2.07	6.88	8.99	2.11	9.95	5.05
<u>Aquic Haplustults</u>											
Jago	0-12	A _p	1.12	1.18	2.04	1.87	6.20	8.10	1.90	8.96	4.93
	13-59	AB	0.76	0.80	1.39	1.27	4.23	5.53	1.29	6.11	5.08
	60-85	B1	0.86	0.91	1.57	1.43	4.77	6.22	1.46	6.89	5.92
<u>Ombroaquic Haplustults</u>											
Origo	0-25	A _p	0.72	0.76	1.31	1.20	3.98	5.20	1.22	5.76	5.01
	26-62	AB	1.01	1.07	1.84	1.69	5.61	7.33	1.72	8.11	4.87
	63-96	B1	0.92	0.97	1.67	1.53	5.08	6.63	1.55	7.34	4.63
	96-149	B2	1.48	1.56	2.70	2.47	8.22	10.73	2.51	11.88	5.06
	150-201	B3	1.15	1.21	2.09	1.92	6.37	8.32	1.95	9.20	4.98

all the soils and it ranged between 3.20 mgkg^{-1} and 10.00 mgkg^{-1} (Table 4). This could be indicative of possibility of Zinc toxicity to plant.

The distribution of exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, Na, and K) was low in most of the soil series. Iwo, Ibadan, Apomu, Jago, and Origo series had low exchangeable bases which could be attributed to their mineralogy and geology. Total exchangeable bases was relatively high in Egbeda, Itaganmodi, Ondo and Gambari.

The distribution of dithionite and oxalate extractable Iron and Aluminum.

The means of profile content of both dithionite- citrate (DC) and oxalate Fe, Al and Mn are given in Table 5. Dithionite extractable - Fe was dominant in all the profiles ranging from $4316.00 \text{ mgkg}^{-1}$ to $75850.00 \text{ mgkg}^{-1}$, Dithionite extractable - Al varied from 691.25 mgkg^{-1} to $5675.00 \text{ mgkg}^{-1}$, Dithionite extractable - Mn was generally low ranging from 24.50 mgkg^{-1} to $1519.00 \text{ mgkg}^{-1}$. Oxalate extractable Fe, Al, and Mn were lower in the soils compared to what was observed for dithionite extractable Fe, Al, and Mn. Oxalate extractable Fe varies from 430.40 mgkg^{-1} to $2203.00 \text{ mgkg}^{-1}$, oxalate Al (301.00 mgkg^{-1} to 1079.2 mgkg^{-1} and Mn (51.20 mgkg^{-1} to $1539.20 \text{ mgkg}^{-1}$). This collaborated the findings of Essoka (2003) when he observed that Dithionite extractable - Fe was more dominant and increased with depth in soils of central Cross Rivers State.

The high value of Dithionite extractable -Fe compared to that of oxalate Fe implies that an appreciable quantity of the free Fe oxide has been transformed into the crystalline form of Iron. The crystalline form of iron is a more advanced stage compared to the amorphous forms that are mobile in

the soil. The crystalline forms of Fe oxides have been found to increase with soil age at the expense of the poorly crystalline forms which tend to reflect in the rate of $\text{Fe}_{(o)}$ to $\text{Fe}_{(d)}$. Low $\text{Fe}_{(o)} / \text{Fe}_{(d)}$ ratio indicate a high degree of crystallinity of Fe oxides (Onweremadu *et al*, 2007). The dithionite extractable iron represents the amounts of the crystalline and amorphous compounds of Fe occurring freely in the soil. Oyediran (1990) concluded that accumulation of free iron oxide in well drained soils could be associated with lessivage, while in hydromorphic soils a zone of Fe accumulation is due to fluctuation in water table (eluviation). Dithionite extractable - Fe was highest in Origo, Ondo, Gambari, Egbeda, Itaganmodi and Ibadan series. It was moderate in Iwo, Jago and lowest in Apomu series.

The $\text{Fe}_{(o)} / \text{Fe}_{(d)}$ ranged from 0.02 to 0.21. There was an evidence of co-migration between dithionite extractable Fe and clay content in some of the soils, Jago, Apomu, Origo and Itaganmodi series show considerable co-migration between dithionite extractable Fe and clay content (Table 5). However, co-migration was observed only in the B horizons in Egbeda and Ibadan series. Dithionite extractable Fe shows a different distribution with depth for the entire soil profile sampled; it increased with depth following the pattern of clay distribution.

The reddening of most of the soil (which were upland soils) subsoil is considered to be due to mobilization and subsequent immobilization of iron during redox-cycles in the soils (Fasina *et al*. (2007); Oyediran and Okusami, (2003)) causing dispersion with progressive oxidation of iron. Okusami and Oyediran, (1985) postulated a biogenetic process for the colouration due to mechanical mixing by plant roots and fauna

Table 4: Means of Some Chemical Properties

Soil series	Depth (cm)	Horizon	Al	Fe	Zn	Meh3. P	T.P	Org.M	Org.C	% T.N.
			—————		(mg/Kg)—————		————— (g/kg) ———			
<u>Rhodic Kandiudox</u>										
Egbeda	0-20	A _p	1.65	0.83	7.05	4.46	376.88	11.31	6.56	0.57
	21-55	AB	1.20	0.60	8.15	0.61	326.88	4.76	2.76	0.24
	56-97	B1	1.38	0.69	9.20	0.71	314.38	5.00	2.90	0.25
	98-130	B2	1.93	0.96	10.00	0.79	341.25	8.12	4.71	0.41
	131-194	B3	0.90	0.49	9.80	0.51	288.30	2.24	1.30	0.11
<u>Typic Kandiudox</u>										
Itangunmodi	0-25	A _p	1.39	0.70	7.50	8.61	399.38	16.46	9.54	0.82
	26-50	AB	2.19	1.10	8.50	5.80	347.50	9.20	5.34	0.46
	51-90	B1	2.59	1.29	9.60	1.70	320.63	6.71	3.89	0.34
	91-150	B2	2.20	1.10	8.55	1.46	339.38	6.32	3.66	0.32
	151-200	B3	3.06	1.53	8.10	2.30	341.25	3.12	1.81	0.16
<u>Arenic Kandiustults</u>										
Iwo	0-25	A _p	2.17	1.09	5.70	70.25	1028.13	13.99	8.11	0.70
	26-59	AB	2.64	1.32	5.95	40.75	475.63	5.97	3.46	0.30
	60-107	B1	1.24	0.62	8.00	30.90	448.13	5.19	3.01	0.26
	108-142	B2	1.53	0.77	8.45	24.50	183.75	5.68	3.29	0.28
	143-198	B3	1.28	0.64	7.25	0.79	169.38	3.77	2.19	0.19
<u>Kanhaplic Haplustults</u>										
Ibadan	0-20	A _p	1.41	0.70	5.90	7.23	235.63	8.55	4.96	0.43
	21-56	AB	2.35	1.18	6.35	4.79	229.38	5.17	3.00	0.26
	57-95	B1	2.95	1.47	6.75	2.03	232.50	8.34	4.84	0.42
	96-134	B2	3.49	1.75	7.10	3.23	262.50	7.40	4.29	0.37
	135-190	B3	2.05	1.02	6.30	0.18	231.25	6.55	3.80	0.33
<u>Udic Paleustalfs</u>										
Gambari	0-15	A _p	1.50	0.75	8.20	9.68	222.50	7.24	4.20	0.36
	16-75	AB	2.20	1.10	8.35	0.86	187.50	6.43	3.73	0.32
	76-140	B1	0.83	0.41	8.75	0.64	148.13	4.31	2.50	0.22
	140-190	B2	0.72	0.36	9.30	0.40	175.63	5.66	3.28	0.28
<u>PlinthicKandiustults</u>										
Ondo	0-30	A _p	1.18	0.59	7.15	1.31	270.00	14.50	8.41	0.73
	30-60	AB	1.52	0.76	8.40	0.29	186.88	5.91	3.43	0.30
	61-100	B1	1.99	1.00	9.10	2.39	226.25	7.57	4.39	0.38
	101-160	B2	1.91	0.95	9.65	0.99	242.50	4.41	2.56	0.22
	161-210	B3	1.96	0.98	7.25	0.50	263.75	3.52	2.04	0.18
<u>Typic Psammaquant</u>										
Apomu	0-30	A _p	0.91	0.46	6.60	5.21	210.00	9.96	5.78	0.50
	30-60	AB	0.94	0.47	7.30	1.54	194.38	4.74	2.75	0.24

Jago	0-12	A _p	1.72	0.86	4.80	3.90	220.00	14.46	8.39	0.72
	13-59	AB	1.18	0.59	5.15	4.28	196.88	3.10	1.80	0.15
	60-85	B	1.32	0.66	4.80	3.00	325.00	4.79	2.78	0.24
<u>Ombroaquic Haplustults</u>										
Origo	0-25	A _p	1.11	0.55	4.35	1.96	331.25	16.41	9.52	0.82
	26-62	AB	1.56	0.78	4.50	0.70	274.38	11.05	6.41	0.55
	63-96	B1	1.41	0.71	5.05	2.48	240.00	7.13	4.14	0.36
	96-149	B2	2.28	1.14	3.80	1.25	246.25	14.44	8.37	0.72
	150-201	B3	1.77	0.88	3.89	1.80	253.75	4.33	2.51	0.22

(termites mainly) this was also collaborated by Obi (2006). The bright subsoil colour in some of the profiles may be an indication of good internal drainage (Oyediran *et al.*, 2004). All the soil profiles were mottled (except Jago), this could be due to lack of mechanical mixing by plant roots and soil fauna. In all the series the percentage clay content increased down the soil profile which could probably justify the recognition of argillic horizon. Okusami and Oyediran (1985) observed that marked weathering and argillation of bed rock to saprolite had taken place in the basement complex of southwestern Nigerian.

Fasina *et al.* (2007) and Ojanuga (1978) concluded that soils of South-western Nigeria are dominant in sesquioxides concretions, ferruginous skeleton, iron nodules and concretions, petroplinthite and quartz materials which are found in the gravelly horizon of the solum. These are indicative of different climate or bioclimate regimes as suggested by Amusan and Ashaye, (1991).

The active ratio of Al_(o) and Al_(d) ranged from 0.10 to 0.69. Agbenin (2003) reported that the ammonium oxalate extraction could be more useful for evaluating amorphous Fe and Al oxides and allophone from sesquioxides soil clay. Based on this, there were little of amorphous Fe oxides in these soils. Active Fe ratio generally decreases with soil depth (Table 4). This indicates that higher proportions of Fe were more in crystalline forms in the lower horizons. Relatively high amounts of active Fe was observed in some of the organic matter rich horizons (within the first 0-30cm of Egbeda, Gambari, and Ondo series)

It was higher in deeper horizons in Itagunmodi, Iwo, Apomu, Jago and Origo series. However, contrary to the report of Oyediran, (1990), most of the Al was more of dithionite form. Generally high correlation exist between Fe₂O_{3(d)}, Al₂O_{3(d)} and clay in the pedons studied ($r=0.651$ and $r=0.774$

irrespective). Oyediran (1990) used Fe₂O_{3(d)}/clay ratio to measure the extent to which Fe₂O_{3(d)} maxima in B horizon are passive i.e. result from either in situ clay formation or co-migration of Fe₂O_{3(d)} with clay resulting to clay illuviation. In Gambari series, Fe₂O_{3(d)}/clay ratio were greater in B horizon (0.29) than A horizons (0.15) (Table 5).

This indicates some Fe₂O_{3(d)} accumulation independent of clay. However, there is a probability that the differences between A and B horizons may be caused by lateral movement of Fe (Robertus and Buol, (1985); Oyediran and Okusami (2004), but because the differences show no systematic trend with either degree of profile development, or slope and landscape position, the higher ratios in B horizon may indicate independent Fe₂O_{3(d)} accumulation.

When the Fe₂O_{3(d)}/clay ratio was fairly uniform with soil depth as observed in Itagunmodi, Iwo, Ibadan, Apomu, Jago, and Origo at the B horizon, it is assumed to be an indication of co-migration or parallel eluviation of iron and clay (Oyediran, 1990). Some soil series like Egbeda, Iwo, Ibadan, Ondo and Origo had high ratios of Fe₂O_{3(d)}/clay in A than in B horizons. This reflects alteration of primary minerals in saprolite and low amount of 'in situ' clay formation.

Conclusion

Nine basement complex soils from southwestern Nigeria that are predominant in the area were studied, The morphological variation noticed in the profile pits used shows that the soils are; highly weathered, this is evident in the reddish to brownish colouration observed in all the series. The amounts and distribution of concretions implies the development of plinthic conditions which is as a result of irreversible reaction of sesquioxide materials. Soil pH ranges from acid to slightly acidic in all the series. The soil texture

Table 5: Mean Distribution of Oxalate Extractable and Dithionite Extractable Fe, Al, Mn.

Soil series	Depth (cm)	Horizon	Al ₂ O ₃ (d)	Fe ₂ O ₃ (d)	Mn _(d) (mg/kg)	Al ₂ O ₃ (o)	Fe ₂ O ₃ (o)	Mn _(o)	Fe ₂ O ₃ (d) / Clay	Fe ₂ O ₃ (o) / Fe ₂ O ₃ (d)	Al ₂ O ₃ (o) / Al ₂ O ₃ (d)
<u>Rhodic Kandiuudox</u>											
Egbeda	0-20	A _p	1488.75	11262.50	783.00	610.80	1163.60	757.40	0.23	0.10	0.41
	21-55	AB	2661.25	25455.00	354.50	583.20	862.00	279.00	0.11	0.03	0.22
	56-97	B1	4529.00	38587.50	804.25	926.40	1296.80	615.80	0.10	0.03	0.20
	98-130	B2	4842.75	40015.00	132.00	957.60	1047.80	99.40	0.12	0.03	0.20
	131-194	B3	3820.00	48011.00	523.00	768.00	1145.00	126.00	0.22	0.02	0.20
<u>Typic Kandiuudox</u>											
Itaganmodi	0-25	A _p	3474.50	24467.50	249.75	878.00	1149.80	262.00	0.10	0.05	0.25
	26-50	AB	4561.25	34037.50	180.00	1034.60	1427.60	163.80	0.08	0.04	0.23
	51-90	B1	4271.00	34135.00	138.50	987.20	1380.40	119.40	0.09	0.04	0.23
	91-150	B2	4646.50	38167.50	146.75	904.00	1242.60	122.20	0.10	0.03	0.19
	151-200	B3	4195.00	31370.00	169.50	1042.80	1778.40	152.00	0.07	0.06	0.25
<u>Arenic Kandiuudox</u>											
Iwo	0-25	A _p	1214.75	10335.00	324.25	648.80	2203.00	310.60	0.17	0.21	0.53
	26-59	AB	1152.25	9559.25	253.00	357.00	844.40	317.00	0.11	0.09	0.31
	60-107	B1	1905.75	17147.50	468.50	551.80	1129.60	477.00	0.08	0.07	0.29
	108-142	B2	1954.00	14843.75	267.00	703.40	999.00	321.00	0.06	0.07	0.36
	143-198	B3	3087.50	31997.50	765.25	859.60	898.20	699.60	0.12	0.03	0.28
<u>Kanhaplic Haplustults</u>											
Ibadan	0-20	A _p	1445.25	12484.75	219.00	477.20	918.20	265.20	0.25	0.07	0.33
	21-56	AB	1467.75	8215.00	202.00	552.00	668.00	230.20	0.05	0.08	0.38

57-95	B1	2920.00	16507.50	169.00	1020.60	897.80	171.40	0.06	0.05	0.35
96-134	B2	2455.25	15580.00	169.25	1011.00	825.00	162.60	0.05	0.05	0.41
135-190	B3	5675.00	70050.00	142.50	995.20	1216.00	350.40	0.18	0.02	0.18
<u>Udic Paleustalfs</u>										
Gambari	A _p	814.00	6015.00	290.75	308.20	453.40	342.20	0.15	0.08	0.38
16-75	AB	2955.25	32255.00	547.50	941.40	892.80	539.40	0.29	0.03	0.32
76-140	B1	3467.50	34425.00	966.75	758.80	886.00	917.40	0.20	0.03	0.22
140-190	B2	3104.25	32502.50	558.75	765.20	862.80	718.00	0.14	0.03	0.25
<u>Plinthic Kandiusults</u>										
Ondo	A _p	3970.25	37422.50	363.25	1062.60	1282.40	313.60	0.42	0.03	0.27
30-60	AB	5209.00	64975.00	885.00	880.20	1258.80	819.20	0.20	0.02	0.17
61-100	B1	5512.50	65200.00	287.50	1079.20	1434.60	331.60	0.18	0.02	0.20
101-160	B2	5281.50	72950.00	830.75	747.00	1207.00	944.80	0.19	0.02	0.14
161-210	B3	4105.00	44875.00	86.25	1022.60	1031.80	187.80	0.12	0.02	0.25
<u>Typic Psammaquant</u>										
Apomu	A _p	779.25	4343.25	199.75	350.80	485.80	284.60	0.06	0.11	0.45
30-60	AB	884.75	5089.25	172.00	301.00	430.40	225.80	0.05	0.08	0.34
61-100	B1	1562.75	9410.00	111.00	428.20	560.20	161.00	0.06	0.06	0.27
101-160	B2	691.25	4316.00	159.50	478.00	560.40	243.40	0.03	0.13	0.69
161-210	B3	3376.00	32995.00	431.50	764.00	1203.20	374.00	0.14	0.04	0.23
<u>Aquic Haplustults</u>										
Jago	A _p	1582.00	10450.00	24.50	342.80	1276.00	51.20	0.07	0.12	0.22
13-59	AB	1832.00	16856.50	215.75	447.00	738.60	191.00	0.08	0.04	0.24
60-85	B1	1937.75	16267.00	230.75	605.20	1135.40	235.20	0.07	0.07	0.31
<u>Ombroaquic Haplustults</u>										
Origo	A _p	1068.75	7367.25	66.25	568.20	969.00	111.80	0.07	0.13	0.53
26-62	AB	1643.25	12077.50	73.25	802.20	1203.00	79.60	0.05	0.10	0.49
63-96	B1	1727.25	13557.50	222.50	757.00	907.40	245.60	0.05	0.07	0.44
96-149	B2	2061.25	18202.50	234.00	951.20	743.00	219.60	0.05	0.04	0.46
150-201	B3	4888.00	75850.00	1519.00	498.80	1198.00	1539.20	0.21	0.02	0.10

Table 8: Correlation Matrix of Fe and Al oxides with some Soil Properties

	CEC	Moisture	pH	%Sand	%Silt	%Clay	Al ₂ O _{3(o)}	Fe ₂ O _{3(o)}	Mn _(o)	Al ₂ O _{3(d)}	Fe ₂ O _{3(d)}	Mn _(d)
CEC												
Moisture	0.157											
pH	0.358	-0.471										
%Sand	-0.418	-0.554	0.201									
%Silt	0.386	-0.055	0.547	-0.266								
%Clay	0.302	0.592	-0.394	-0.945	-0.064							
Al ₂ O _{3(o)}	0.374	0.645	-0.228	-0.895	0.152	0.875						
Fe ₂ O _{3(o)}	0.425	0.533	-0.150	-0.533	0.181	0.490	0.551					
Mn _(o)	0.037	0.342	0.225	-0.347	0.448	0.207	0.375	0.206				
Al ₂ O _{3(d)}	0.292	0.707	-0.346	-0.904	0.064	0.914	0.903	0.490	0.451			
Fe ₂ O _{3(d)}	0.245	0.722	-0.332	-0.858	0.149	0.838	0.811	0.486	0.540	0.961		
Mn _(d)	0.041	0.376	0.181	-0.421	0.399	0.300	0.434	0.256	0.986	0.516	0.587	

Correlation at p<0.01

varied from sandy at the epipedon to clayey at the subsoil. The distribution of sesquioxides varies greatly among the soils.

Dithionite extractable Al and Fe were more predominant in all the soils and increases with depth. This shows that crystalline form of Al and Fe are the major constituents of these soils which could have resulted from high rate of weathering that had taken place over time on the initial parent materials. The mineralogy and geology of the parent materials, climate and relief of the area may also play a significant role in the final distribution and forms that were observed. The amorphous forms (oxalate extractable) of Al and Fe were less in quantity and distribution. However, their presences were highly significant. The high proportion of crystalline forms of Al and Fe could lead to structural distortion that could have implication for anion retention, affect surface area and lead to hardness of the soil and aid plinthite development. This will have effect on the physical and chemical properties of the soils, thus affect the subsequent management and land use patterns of the soils. Also, there is evidence of co-migration of Fe_(d) and clay content in some of the soils

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